

PRELIMINARY DESIGN OF UNSTIFFENED COMPOSITE SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

Preliminary design calculations for statically determinate composite unstiffened shells which experience local stresses due to holes, special cut-outs, free edges and which may experience out-of-plane transverse stresses associated with the local bending moment and shell curvature are discussed. A failure criteria that was derived in a previous work is applied to calculate the local failure of an elliptic unstiffened shell.

INTRODUCTION

In (ref. 1), a rate-dependent failure criteria for composite structures is introduced. In this criteria, it is proposed that a composite structural point or structure fails at a stress state where the rate of inelastic strain energy permanently stored in it equals the rate of strain energy pumped into it. The criteria takes the following mathematical forms:

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^3 \sigma_{ij} \frac{d\epsilon_{ij}^i}{dt} \geq \sum_{i,j=1}^3 \sigma_{ij} \frac{d\epsilon_{ij}^t}{dt} \quad (1)$$

$$\int_V \sum_{i,j=1}^3 \sigma_{ij} \frac{d\epsilon_{ij}^i}{dt} \geq \int_V \sum_{i,j=1}^3 \sigma_{ij} \frac{d\epsilon_{ij}^t}{dt} \quad (2)$$

for structural point failure and complete structural failure respectively. The tensor, σ_{ij} , is the Cauchy stress tensor and t is time. The inelastic and total strain tensors are ϵ_{ij}^i and ϵ_{ij}^t , respectively. The integrations of (eqn. 2) are taken over the structure volume, V . Experimental failure data for (0/-30/30)_{3S} carbon fiber/epoxy coupons with a central hole are used to verify the validity of the theory in (ref.1). In this paper, the effect of the local stress concentration due to holes, special cut-outs, free edges and the transverse axial stresses associated with the local bending stresses and shell curvature are considered. Example for preliminary local failure design calculations of simple statically determinate unstiffened shells are given for illustration purposes.

TANGENTIAL STRESSES AROUND A HOLE

Consider a composite plate with a hole of radius r_0 and remote applied stresses σ_χ , σ_ξ and $\tau_{\xi\chi}$ where σ_χ is in the direction of maximum principal in plane stiffness, E_1 , as shown in (fig. 1). The elasticity solution for the tangential continuum stresses $\sigma_{\theta 0}$ around hole at an angle β is given in (ref.2), by:

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$$\sigma_w = \frac{\{-k\sigma_x + k(k+n)\sigma_\xi\} \cos^2 \beta + \{-k\sigma_\xi + (1+n)\sigma_x\} \sin^2 \beta - \tau_{\chi\xi}(1+k+n)n \sin 2\beta}{k^2 \cos^4 \beta + \left(\frac{E_1}{G_{12}} - 2\mu_{12}\right) \sin^2 \beta \cos^2 \beta + \sin^4 \beta} \quad (3)$$

where, $k=(E_1/E_2)^{0.5}$, and, $n=[2(k^2-\mu_{12})+E_1/G_{12}]^{0.5}$

Figure 1-In-plane stresses applied to a hole in the shell Figure 2- Hole spacing in orthotropic material

The constants E_1 , E_2 and G_{12} are elasticity constants and μ_{12} is Poisson's ratio. The value of β at which the maximum value of the local stress σ_{t0} occurs is obtained by maximizing (eqn. 3) with respect to β .

MINIMUM HOLE SPACING

Consider a single applied stress σ_χ parallel to the major material principal axes. The stress along the line $\beta = \text{constant}$ is assumed to decay as follows:

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_w \cos\left(w \frac{r}{r_0}\right) \text{Exp}\left(-w \frac{r}{r_0}\right) \quad (4)$$

where σ_{t0} is given by (eqn. 3) while r is a radial distance measured from the edge of the hole and r_0 is the hole diameter. The stress distribution of (eqn.4) is represented as a damped sinusoidal function which frequency and damping are controlled by the parameter, w . The tangent stress σ_t , at an angle $\beta = \pi/2$, generates a force $= 4hr_0\sigma_\chi$ that balances the reduction in the resisting force due to the hole, where the thickness of the laminate is $2h$. Therefore, it follows that:

$$4hr_0\sigma_x = 4h \frac{r_0}{w} \sigma_w \left(\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \int_0^\infty \cos\left(w \frac{r}{r_0}\right) \text{Exp}\left(-w \frac{r}{r_0}\right) d\left(w \frac{r}{r_0}\right) = 2h \frac{r_0}{w} (1+n) \sigma_x \quad (5)$$

from which, it follows that:

$$w = \frac{(1+n)}{2} \quad (6)$$

If σ_ξ only is applied, it can be shown that:

$$w = \frac{(k+n)}{2k} \quad (7)$$

The secondary stresses are negligible at a distance $r=d$, at which $w(d/r_0)=2\pi$. Therefore, the holes centers should be spaced by a distance greater than $(d+2r_0)$ which is given for holes loaded in-plane, in the strong and weak material principal directions by:

$$d = 2r_0 \left(\frac{2\pi}{n+1} + 1 \right) \quad \text{and} \quad d = 2r_0 \left(\frac{2\pi k}{n+k} + 1 \right) \quad (8)$$

respectively. For isotropic materials, $k=1$ and $n=2$, therefore, the minimum hole spacing is approximately three times the hole diameter. For composite materials, according to (eqn. 8), the holes loaded in the strong material direction can be more closely spaced while the holes loaded in the weak material direction are more spaced than the isotropic material, as shown in (fig. 2).

LOCAL STRESSES DUE TO SPECIAL CUT-OUTS

Cut-outs are mandatory in composite shell structures for a variety of reasons. Therefore, the tangential stress for special cut-outs, (fig. 3), is considered in this section. The considered set of cut-outs are represented geometrically in x-y plane by the following implicit equations.

$$x = \lambda(\cos\beta + \omega \cos N\beta), \quad y = \lambda(c \sin\beta - \omega \sin N\beta) \quad (9)$$

The parameter N , which is an integer and the parameters c and ω adjust the shape of the cut-out to make it an equilateral triangle or a square with rounded corners, a circle, ellipse or oval as shown in (fig. 3). The parameter λ , controls the size of the hole. In (ref. 3), a perturbation technique is used to obtain the stress tangent to the cut-out boundary as a series expansions of σ_χ , σ_ξ and $\tau_{\chi\xi}$ up the third order. The formulas of (ref. 2), are simplified to a first order approximation as follows:

$$\sigma_\omega = \sigma_x \left[\frac{B^2}{C^2} + \frac{1}{LC^2} \{c(AD^4 \cos\phi + BC^4 \sin\beta) - \omega N(AD^4 \cos N\beta + BC^4 n \sin N\beta)\} \right] + \sigma_y \left[\frac{A^2}{C^2} + \frac{1}{LC^2} \{ (AC^4 \cos\beta + BE^4 \sin\beta) + \omega N(AC^4 kn \cos N\beta + BE^4 \sin N\beta) \} \right] - \tau_{xy} \left[\frac{2n(1+k+n)AB}{LC^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

where

$$A = c \cos\beta - \omega N \cos N\beta, \quad B = \sin\beta - \omega N \sin N\beta, \quad C^2 = A^2 + B^2$$

$$D^4 = -A^4 k + A^2 B^2 (1 - 2k - k^2) + B^4 (2 + k - n^2)$$

$$E^4 = A^4 (2k^2 - n^2 + k) + A^2 B^2 (k^2 - 2k - 1) - B^4 k$$

$$L = B^4 + k^2 A^4 + (n^2 - 2k) A^2 B^2$$

Figure 3- Special cut-outs

The maximum tangential stress obtained from (eqn.10) is approximately equal to the maximum tangential stresses of (ref. 3). At small stresses (near zero), the error of (eqn. 10) in evaluating the tangential stress increases dramatically. However, the error in evaluating the negligible stresses can be disregarded as long as the design is based on the safety of high stress level points.

FREE-EDGE STRESSES

In, (fig. 4), a laminate is loaded in the x direction by a stress σ_x where the free edge is perpendicular to the y axes. The stress σ_x develops in-plane stresses σ_{x0}^i , σ_{y0}^i and τ_{xy0}^i in the i^{th} ply, which are given from laminate theory by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x0}^i \\ \sigma_{y0}^i \\ \tau_{xy0}^i \end{bmatrix} = \left(\frac{1}{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2} \right) \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11}^i & Q_{12}^i & Q_{16}^i \\ Q_{12}^i & Q_{22}^i & Q_{26}^i \\ Q_{16}^i & Q_{16}^i & Q_{66}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_{22} \\ -A_{12} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \sigma_x \quad (11)$$

where Q_{ij}^i is the stiffness matrix of the i^{th} ply while A_{ij} is the laminate extensional stiffness matrix. At the free edge, the stresses σ_{y0}^i and τ_{xy0}^i are equal to zero. They develop to the values given by (eqn. 11) within a "boundary layer thickness", d , in which the stress state is triaxial. A composite laminate of thickness $2h$, is build of repeated building blocks which thickness is T . The stresses σ_{y0}^i and τ_{xy0}^i are periodical functions of z with a period equal to $2T$. The fully developed continuum laminate stresses, σ_{y0} and τ_{xy0} , are therefore expanded as a Fourir expansion and the first term only is used in the analysis of this paper as follows:

$$\sigma_{y0} = \sigma_{y00} \cos \pi \frac{z}{T}, \quad \tau_{xy0} = \tau_{xy00} \sin \pi \frac{z}{T} \quad (12)$$

where σ_{y00} and τ_{xy00} are the maximum in-plane axial stress and the maximum transverse shear stress in the laminate. The stresses σ_{y0} and τ_{xy0} are assumed to vary in the y direction according to the following relationships:

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_{y00} \cos \pi \frac{z}{T} [1 - e^{-\gamma \frac{z}{h}} (\cos \gamma \frac{y}{h} + \sin \gamma \frac{y}{h})] \quad (13)$$

$$\tau_{xy} = \tau_{xy00} \sin \pi \frac{z}{T} \left[1 - e^{-\gamma \frac{z}{h}} \cos \gamma \frac{y}{h} \right] \quad (14)$$

where $\gamma=(1+n)/2$, in the strong material direction while $\gamma=(n+k)/2k$, in the weak material direction. A mathematical structure for the distribution of σ_y and τ_{xy} in the y direction similar to that of (eqns.13,14) was used in (ref. 3) in which the functions σ_{y0} and τ_{xy0} are represented as general function of z , which made the calculation of the interlaminar stresses rather cumbersome. Also, the value of γ presented in (eqn. 13,14) are material dependent while in (ref. 3), it is not clear how to choose γ for different materials. The introduction of the harmonic stress distribution of σ_{y0} and τ_{xy0} by (eqn. 12) and the satisfaction of stress equilibrium provides the interlaminar stresses represented in the following simple form:

$$\tau_{yz} = \frac{4\sigma_{y00}\gamma}{\pi m} \sin \pi \frac{z}{T} e^{-\gamma z} \sin \gamma y \quad (15)$$

$$\tau_{xz} = \frac{2\tau_{xy00}\gamma}{\pi m} \cos \pi \frac{z}{T} e^{-\gamma z} (\sin \gamma y + \cos \gamma y) \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_x = \frac{8\sigma_{y00}\gamma^2}{\pi^2 m^2} \cos \pi \frac{z}{T} e^{-\gamma z} (\cos \gamma y - \sin \gamma y) \quad (17)$$

where $m=2h/T$, equals the number of repeated building blocks in the laminate. Notice that the interlaminar stresses decrease as the number of laminate building blocks increases. It follows that the maximum interlaminar stresses near a free edge are given by:

$$\tau_{yz} = 0.41 \frac{\sigma_{y00}\gamma}{m}, \quad \tau_{xz} = 0.64 \frac{\tau_{xy00}\gamma}{m}, \quad \sigma_x = 0.17 \frac{\sigma_{y00}\gamma^2}{m^2} \quad (18)$$

These stresses should be introduced in the calculations of local failure near a free edge.

Figure 6- Free edge in-plane applied stress

Figure 5- Local bending stresses in the shell

INTERLAMINAR NORMAL STRESS DUE TO CURVATURE

The work in (ref. 4) for the calculation of interlaminar normal stress in a curved beam is extended in this section to a curved shell, where the interaction of shell curvature and bending stresses develop a transverse axial stress. Transverse axial stresses arise from the equilibrium of transverse forces and are therefore independent of material properties. Consider a curved laminate with two principal radii of curvature R_θ and R_ϕ as shown in (fig. 5). The bending stresses σ_θ and σ_ϕ are represented as linear functions of the thickness as follows

$$\sigma_\theta = \sigma_{\theta b} \frac{z}{h} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_\phi = \sigma_{\phi b} \frac{z}{h} \quad (19)$$

where, $\sigma_{\theta b}$ and $\sigma_{\phi b}$, are the maximum bending stresses. These stresses develop an axial transverse stress, σ_z , which is obtained from the transverse stress equilibrium and is given as follows:

$$\sigma_z = -\left(1 - \frac{z^2}{h^2}\right) \left(\frac{h}{2}\right) \left[\frac{\sigma_{\theta b}}{R_\theta} + \frac{\sigma_{\phi b}}{R_\phi}\right] \quad (20)$$

where the maximum value of, σ_z , occurs at $z=0$.

EXAMPLE CALCULATION #1: Continuous shell

This example calculation considers a submarine idealized as an elliptic composite shell which is manufactured from Carbon/Epoxy with 60% volume fraction, Table 1. The shell is built, such that the latitudes and meridians are the principle laminate directions. In the first example, it is assumed that the marine shell is continuous and it is required to obtain the maximum depth it may reach at a given rate of decent. The stresses in the skin of the ellipsoid are in-plane stresses which are independent of the skin material property and are given in (ref. 5) by:

Figure 6- Elliptic shell dimensions and angle definition

Figure 7-Failure Applied Pressure

$$\sigma_\phi = \frac{pc}{4hf} \left[\frac{ab}{c^2} - \left(\frac{a}{b} - \frac{b}{a} \right) \cos 2\theta \right]$$

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{pcf}{4h} \left[\frac{ab}{c^2} + \left(\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{a} - 2\frac{ab}{c^2} \right) \sin^2 \phi + \left(\frac{a}{b} - \frac{b}{a} \right) \cos^2 \phi \cos 2\theta \right]$$

$$\tau_{\theta\phi} = \frac{pc}{4h} \left[\left(\frac{a}{b} - \frac{b}{a} \right) \cos \phi \sin 2\theta \right]$$

where

$$f = \sqrt{c^2 + (b^2 - a^2) \cos^2 \theta + (b^2 - c^2) \cos^2 \phi + (a^2 - b^2) \cos^2 \phi \cos^2 \theta} \quad (21)$$

The principal axis a,b and c shown in (fig. 6) are measured along the x,y and z axis of the ellipsoid. The angle θ is measured in the yz plane and is zero at the x axis. The angle ϕ is measured in the xz plane and is zero also at the x axis. The shell is assumed to be a surface of revolution which diameters are $a=4$ meters (160 inches), $b=4$ meters (160 inches) and $c= 10.0$ meters(400 inches). First the shell is built such that the ϕ directions (generators) of the

shell have the maximum modulus E_1 . The application of (eqn. 1) to the stress state of (eqn. 21) and using the inelastic strain rate equation in (ref. 2) shows that the initial in-plane local failure occurs at the latitude ring at $\phi = 90.0$ degrees where the stresses are $\sigma_\phi = 73$ MPa and $\sigma_\theta = 133$ MPa. The use of other equations for the inelastic flow of the anisotropic composite material may lead to slight difference in these stresses. External pressure at failure depends on the rate of submarine decent as follows:

$$p_r = 0.98 \left(\frac{dp}{dt} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r}} \quad (22)$$

Such that, under a rate of decent of 1 meter/sec, the shell fails at approximately 10 atmospheric pressures (100 meters depth in water). Next the material is oriented such that θ directions (latitudes) are associated with E_1 . The application of (eqn. 1) in this case, shows that the initial in-plane local failure occur also at the latitude ring at $\phi = 90$ degrees where the stresses are $\sigma_\phi = 89$ MPa and $\sigma_\theta = 164$ MPa. Failure in this case occurs at an external pressure given by:

$$p_r = 1.20 \left(\frac{dp}{dt} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r}} \quad (23)$$

Such that, at a rate of decent of 1 meter/sec, the shell fails at approximately 12.24 atmospheres (122.4 meters depth in water). The failure loads of (eqns. 22,23) are plotted in (fig.7), where the pressure is measured in MPa. Notice that , for the same amount of material, the second composite material orientation allows the submarine to sustain more pressure before failure occurs. The explanation is simple. The submarine shell fails under compression at a point where the latitude directions experience more compression stress in the generators directions. The E_1 direction has a larger compression strength, Table 1, such that by placing the E_1 in the latitude directions we get more load carrying capacity.

EXAMPLE CALCULATION #2: The shell with a hatch

The shell of the submarine can not be continuous. A square hatch with rounded corners (fig.8) which side is 30" is used to allow access. The center of the hatch is placed at $\phi=90^\circ$. The "remote" stresses for the hatch are assumed to be equal to the stress in the continuous shell at the position of the center of the hatch. It follows from (eqn.10) that the tangential stresses of the hatch at points A and B shown (fig. 8) are given for the first material orientation by:

Figure 8-Shell hatch stiffening

Figure 9-Shell assembly

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\theta A} &= 7.73\sigma_\phi - 4.82\sigma_\theta = +82 \text{ MPa} \\ \sigma_{\theta B} &= -.53\sigma_\phi + 3.63\sigma_\theta = -603 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

For the second material orientation, these stresses are given by:

$$\sigma_{\text{toA}} = 3.63\sigma_p - 0.53\sigma_o = -236 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{toB}} = -4.83\sigma_p + 7.73\sigma_o = -839 \text{ MPa} \quad (25)$$

The logarithmic relationship shown in (fig. 7) indicates that for a wide range of rates of loading, the unidirectional strength of the composite material under consideration is approximated by the failure strengths in Table 1. It is shown from (eqns 1,21) that the compressive failure stress for the first and second material orientations are 289 MPa(41 Ksi) and 326MPa(46.Ksi) respectively. The stress σ_{toB} is enough to fail the skin in compression at all practical rates of loading for both material orientations. The excess in the edge stress of (eqn. 24,25) is local and decreases exponentially away from the edge. The distance at which these secondary stresses are reduced to 5% of their maximum values at the edge is given by:

$$d_1 = 3 \frac{h}{\gamma} \quad (26)$$

The thickness of the laminate equals $2h=60 \times 3 \times .16=28.8$ mm. For the first material orientation, this distance d_1 is given by $d_1=3 \times 14.4/2.41=18$ mm, while for the second orientation it equals $d_1=3 \times 14.4/1.41=31.6$ mm. The compressive tangent free edge stresses develop sinusoidal axial and shear stresses, (eqn. 13,14). The magnitude of these stresses are obtained from (eqn. 11) and are given for the material in (Table 1) by:

$$\sigma_{yoo} = 0.53\sigma_o \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{xyoo} = 0.03\sigma_o \quad (27)$$

The only non zero transverse stress at the edge is σ_z , which value, according to (eqn. 20), equals 0.01 MPa for the first case and 0.02 MPa, which is negligible. To eliminate the local failure of the edge at point B, for a rate of decent of 1 m/sec, the thickness has to be increased to $d_2=(603/289) \times 28.8=60.1$ mm for the first case of material orientation and to $d_2=(839/326) \times 28.8=74.12$ mm for the second case. From the above discussion, the local failure of the hatch can be prevented for both orientations by forming a lip at the free edge which depth is 61.4 mm in the first case and 76.2 mm in the second case as shown in (fig.8).

Table 1.-Material elastic constants and failure strength for (0/30/-30)₃ Carbon fiber/ Epoxy laminate
The failure strengths(F) are estimated at a strain rate of 2.2E-4 in/in/sec
Repeated building block is (0/30/-30), Ply thickness=0.16 mm

E ₁ =97.20 GPa	F1t=936.0 MPa	F1c=326 MPa
E ₂ =14.80 GPa	F2t=70.00 MPa	F2c=289 MPa
E ₃ =11.80 GPa	F3t=75.00 MPa	F3c=251.MPa
G ₁₂ =24.50 GPa	F12=153 MPa	
G ₂₃ =5.200 GPa	F23=102 MPa	
G ₁₃ =5.200 GPa	F13=102 Mpa	
$\mu_{12}=1.21$		

EXAMPLE #3: Shell assembly

A submarine is built from two symmetric substructures, cut along the xy plane, which are assembled by adhesive and rivets of diameter $2r_o$. The second material orientation of example#1 is used in the construction. In the first assembly, (a), the rivets carry no load, since the shell is under pressure and the assembly is taking place along planes of symmetry. However, the lip acts as a cantilever and is subjected to distributed pressure which is assumed linear. The bending moment associated with the linear pressure distribution is estimated by:

$$M_r = \frac{LR}{6} P_f \quad (28)$$

where, L, is the length of the lip and , R, is the shell radius of revolution at the assembly section. This bending moment reacts with the shell curvature to produce a transverse stress, (eqn. 20) given by , $\sigma_z=LRP_f/8hp$, where ρ is the radius of curvature of the bent lip. For a shell radius of $R=4$ meters (160 inches), $h=14.4$ mm (0.57 inches) and a maximum external pressure of , $P_f=1.2$ MPa, and a transverse compressive failure strength of , 251 MPa, it follows that , $L < 6.02 \rho$. Such that, for $\rho=50.8$ mm (2 inches), the maximum allowable length of the lip equals , $L=302$ mm (12. inches).

In the second assembly , (b), the two shell substructures are assembled by an interior and an exterior ring connected to the shell substructures by adhesive , to eliminate the secondary bending moment in the skin. If the bolts are

designed to transfer all the compression force from one shell side to the other whenever the adhesive fails (fail safe design), then the total cross section of the bolts, A_b , is estimated as follows:

$$A_b = \pi h R \frac{\sigma_{cs}}{\sigma_{sb}} \quad (29)$$

where, σ_{cs} , is the compressive strength of the skin in the direction of the shell generators, while, σ_{sb} , is the bolt shear strength. The disadvantage with the, (b), assembly is that a large total cross sectional area of bolts may be needed for the assembly especially for strong composites, which may weaken the structure along the assembly lines. In the third possible assembly, (c), the shells are stepped down and assembled by adhesive. This assembly avoids the bending and bolting problems of assemblies (a) and (b). However, it has the disadvantage that, due to the bouncy forces and the shell weight distribution, there could be a shear force on the stepped down shell connection. This shear force develops a local bending moment that may lead to the local failure of the stepped down shell. The, (d), assembly where the step down is gradual may present a better local bending stiffness of the step down shell cross section.

EXAMPLE CALCULATION#4: Bolt spacing

The stress concentration factor in the strong material direction equals $(1+n)=(1+3.83)=4.83$, while in the weak material direction, it equals $(k+n)/k=(2.56+3.83)/2.56=2.49$. The free edges need to be supported by increasing the skin thickness locally 4.83 times to make it equals to $4.83*180*.16=139.1$ mm. The minimum rivet spacing in the zy plane is given by (eqn. 8) as, $d=4.6r_0$. The minimum rivet spacing in the xy plane is given by (eqn. 8) as, $d=7.53r_0$

DISCUSSION

In the composite shell design calculation examples considered in this paper, it is noticed that the shell cut-outs, bolts and rivet holes and free edges develop a stress concentration that requires special stiffening of the shell to avoid local in-plane failure of the shell. Also parasite secondary bending stresses may arise at the assembly sections, which reacts with the shell curvature and may lead to delamination of the composite skin. If the technology allows it, it is best to build the composite shell in one piece to avoid local failure in assembly sections. Otherwise the number of substructures to be assembled should be minimized. It is also noticed that based on strength calculations (shell buckling is not considered in this paper), the unstiffened composite carbon fiber shell of 60% fiber volume fraction and a thickness of 28.8 mm (1.13 inches) can not go beyond 122.4 meters depth. The use of stiffened panels, which are stiffened by rings and stringers assembled with the skin by adhesives may present a better alternative design concept for designs having a higher strength failure loads and buckling failure loads for the same composite weight.

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